

Checklist of rotifer species from Albania (phylum Rotifera)

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Abstract. The checklist of Rotifera species recorded for Albanian inland waters and its neighboring regions is provided. A total of 140 species of bdelloids and monogononts, with representatives of 38 genera are listed. The history of rotifer surveys as a component of zooplankton in Albania started at the end of 19th century. Mostly they were taxonomic and descriptive ones, while later on after the mid 20th century appeared the systematic approaches emphasizing the particularities and richness of zooplankton in specific karstic Mediterranean ecosystems. In this article 140 taxa of bdelloids and monogononts representing 39 genera are reported.

Keywords. Rotifera, Albania, checklist, inland water, distribution records

INTRODUCTION

Albania is a small country (Fig. 1) however, it is rich in water resources including lakes, rivers and springs. There are more than 152 streams and small rivers flow into the seven large rivers, Buna, Drini, Mati, Erzeni, Shkumbini, Semani, and Vjosa, which run southeast to north west towards the Adriatic coast (Cullaj *et al.* 2005). About 247 natural lakes are dispersed throughout the country, most of karstic or glacial origin and they are often very small (less than 1 ha). Albania shares with neighboring countries three of the largest Balkanic Lakes (Ohrid, Prespa and Shkodra). They represent distinct environments among all aquatic habitats of the Balkan in the view of origin, hydrology, and biodiversity (Shumka *et al.* 2018). Around 134 glacial lakes are situated mainly in the northeastern part of the country at altitudes between 1500 – 1800 m a.s.l. Generally, they are small, formed mainly over magmatic (mainly of ultrabasics) and terrene formations (Cullaj *et al.* 2005).

Following Segers (2007) the Phylum Rotifera comprises about 2030 known species worldwide and classified in three main groups, the marine Seisonida (4 species), the Monogononta (1570

species) and the unique, exclusively parthenogenetic Bdelloidea with 461 clonal species. Although the morphology of different species varies widely, all of them possess a specialized masticatory organ containing a set of densely sclerotized trophi (Fontaneto *et al.* 2008). Rotifers, as a component of zooplankton organisms, comprise crucial elements of the structure and function of freshwater ecosystems, not only as consumers of algae, bacteria, protozoans and other invertebrates (Russell *et al.* 2010), but also as food items for juvenile stages of several fish species (Shumka *et al.* 2018). Moreover, their pivotal role in freshwater ecosystems food web, as well as its sensitivity to both man-made and natural changes, makes zooplankton quite suitable for assessing alterations in the trophic dynamics and the ecological state of aquatic ecosystems related to changes in nutrient loading and climate (Hoffmann 1977, Ferrara *et al.* 2002, Preston & Rusak 2010).

Similarly to other large Balkanic lakes like Ohrid and Prespa, the history of zooplankton surveys in Albania starts from the end of 19th century. Basically they were taxonomic and descriptive ones, while later, after the mid 20th century appeared the systematic approach emphasizing

Figure 1. Map of Albania

the particularities and richness of zooplankton in specific karstic Mediterranean ecosystem. Amongst them can be mention Richard (1897) with his work dedicated to *Cladocera*, Steur (1900) with paper published on *Copepoda*, Vereščagin (1912) and Parenzan (193) on *Cladocera*, Nedeljković (1959) on *Rotifera*, Petkovski (1961) with fundamental work on *Cladocera* and *Copepoda*, separately *Harpacticoida* and *Ostracoda*, Živković (1965) and Milovanović & Živković (1965) on Rotifera, Protozoa and Cladocera.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are a large number of references, including identification keys with abundant information on ecological and systematical aspects of rotifers from different regions of the world. From this, the following papers were consulted: Segers (2002) and Wallace *et al.* (2006); higher-level classification. For taxonomy and distribution of the different families the following sources were used: De Ridder (1986, 1991, 1993), De Ridder & Segers (1997), Donner (1965), De Smet (2006), De Smet & Pourriot (1997), Jersabek (2003), Koste (1978), Koste & Shiel (1987, 1989a, b), Nogrady *et al.*, (1995), Nogrady & Segers (2002), Segers (1995a, b, 2003), Segers & Wallace (2001), Sørensen *et al.* (2005).

The following articles were used to compile the list of rotifers of Albanian inland waters: Brusina (1898), Byron (1981), Gannon & Stemberger (1981), Guseska (2012), Guseska *et al.* (2008, 2012, 2014), Gushevska *et al.* (1996), Kiefer (1937), Kostoski (1998), Kostoski *et al.* (2004, 2005), Michaloudi (2005), Michaloudi *et al.* (1997), Milovanovic & Živkovic (1965), Nedeljkovic (1959), Parenzan (1931), Petković (1973, 1975, 1978, 1981), Popovska-Stanković *et al.* (1988, 2003), Richard (1897), Serafimova-Hadzisce (1954, 1958, 1975), Shumka (1994, 1997a, b, 2000, 2001, 2014), Shumka & Miho (2006), Shumka & Nikleka (2018), Shumka & Špoljar (2018), Shumka *et al.* (1998, 2018), Steuer (1900), Tasevska (2002), Tasevska *et al.* (2006, 2008, 2012a, b, 2017, 2018), Verščagin (1912), Živkovic (1974, 1975),

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All species names appeared in the literature listed above were checked and corrected based on Segers *et al.* 2007 and Jersabek & Leitner 2013, and the following changes were made: *Brachionus calyciflorus* f. *amphiceros* (Ehrenberg, 1838) (synonym, considered an infrasubspecific variant of *B. calyiflorus*); *Brachionus* q. f. *brevispinus* Ehrenberg, 1832 (synonym, considered an infra

subspecific variant of *B. quadridentatus*); *Brachionus* q. f. *cluniorbicularis* Skorikov, 1894 (synonym considered an infrasubspecific variant of *B. quadridentatus*); *Brachionus quadridentatus* f. *rhenanus* Lauterborn, 1893, (synonym considered an infrasubspecific variant of *B. quadridentatus*); *Lophocharis salpina* (Ehrenberg, 1834) synonym of *Lepadella salpina* Ehrenberg, 1834; *Testudinella patina trilobata* (Anderson et Shepard, 1892), synonym of *T. patina* (Hermann 1783); *Testudinella pseudoelliptica* Bartoš, 1951 synonym of *T. patina* (Hermann 1783); *Trichocerca similis similis* (Wierzejski, 1893) synonymous with *Rattulus bicornis* (Western, 1893).

Reviewing the studies dedicated to the Albanian inland water Rotifera fauna is resulted in a list of 140 taxa of bdelloids and monogononts (Table 1). Among the rotifers, the most frequently reported genera are *Lecane* with 16 species, *Trichocerca* with 15 species, *Brachionus* (15 species), *Keratella* (7 species), *Polyarthra* (7 species) and *Lepadella* (6 species). At regional scale it is worth mentioning that from the neighboring Montenegro Petković (1973, 1978) recorded 205 rotifer taxa just for the Lake Scadar/Shkodra, while from North Macedonia for the lakes Ohrid,

Prespa and Dojran altogether 60 rotifer taxa were reported (Tasevska *et al.* 2006). However, the high number of species reported for the Lake Scadar/Shkodra by Petković (1973, 1978) does not reflect the latest taxonomic results of Segers *et al.*, (2007) and Jersabek & Leitner (2013) listing numerous synonym names and corrections.

The biogeography of Rotifera is highly controversial and prior to the work of Dumont (1983) it was generally accepted that all taxa were cosmopolitan. In the present list of the Albanian rotifers most of the species show a typical Palearctic distribution (Segers 2007) however, to clear the biogeography of several widely distributed species further studies with molecular approaches are needed.

Based on the data presented in the Table 1 almost 90% of the species are found in the Drini Basin (including Lakes of Lesser and Macro Prespa, Ohrid and Scadar/Shkodra), while the transitional water bodies belonging to Ionian and Adriatic Coastal areas are populated only by 9 different species. This disproportional distribution of species calls for further studies.

Table 1. List of Bdelloidea and Monogononta rotifers recorded from continental fresh- and transitional water habitats in Albania (genus and species)

Taxon	Locality (water basins)	References
<i>Adineta</i> Hudson & Gosse, 1886		
<i>A. steineri</i> Bartos, 1951	A5 (A)	14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41,42
<i>Anuraeopsis</i> Lauterborn, 1900		
<i>A. fissa</i> Gosse, 1851	A1, A2, A5 (A)	12, 13, 15, 17
<i>A. coelata</i> de Beauchamp, 1932	A5 (A)	12, 13, 15, 17, 30, 31, 32
<i>Ascomorpha</i> Perty, 1850		
<i>A. ecaudis</i> Perty, 1850	A5, B1, B2 (A, B)	12, 13, 15, 17, 30, 31, 32
<i>A. ovalis</i> Carlin, 1943	A2, A5, B1 (A, B)	
<i>A. saltans</i> Bartsch, 1870	A5 (A)	12, 13, 14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>Asplanchna</i> Gosse, 1850		
<i>A. girodide</i> Guerne, 1888	A5 (A)	14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>A. priodonta</i> Gosse, 1850	A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, B1, B2, C1	
<i>A. sieboldii</i> Leydig, 1854	A5 (A)	12, 13, 14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>Brachionus</i> Pallas, 1766		
<i>B. angularis</i> Gosse, 1851	A1, A2, A3, A5, B1, B2, C1, C2, C2, C4, C5, D1 (A, B, C, D)	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>B. bidentatus</i> Anderson, 1889	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>B. calyciflorus</i> Pallas, 1776	A5, B2 (A, B)	12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 29, 31, 32, 38, 40
<i>B. dimidiatus</i> Bryce, 1931	A5 (A)	12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42

<i>B. diversicornis</i> Daday, 1883	A1, A2, A5 (A)	2, 3, 10, 11, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25
<i>B. falcatus</i> Zacharias, 1898	A5 (A)	12, 13, 31, 32, 42
<i>B. forficula</i> Wierzejski, 1891	A1, A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>B. havanaensis</i> Rousselet, 1911	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>B. leydigii</i> Cohn, 1862	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>B. plicatilis</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A5, B1 (A, B)	12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 29, 31, 32, 38, 40
<i>B. rhenanus</i> Lauterborn, 1893.	A5, B1 (A, B)	12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 29, 31
<i>B. quadridentatus</i> Hermann, 1783	A1, A3, A4, A5, B2. (A, B)	12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 29, 31, 32, 38, 40
<i>B. brevispinus</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>B. quadridentatus melhemi</i> Barrios et Daday, 1894	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>B. urceolaris</i> O.F. Müller, 1773	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
Cephalodella Bory de St. Vincent, 1826		
<i>C. catellina</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>C. forficula</i> Ehrenberg, 1831	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>C. gibba</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A2, A3, A5 (A)	10, 11, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22
<i>C. misgurnus</i> Wulfert, 1937	A5. (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>C. ventripes</i> Dixon-Nuttall, 1901	A5, C1 (A, C)	13, 14, 15, 29, 31, 32, 38, 42
Collotheca Harring, 1913		
<i>C. mutabilis</i> Hudson, 1885	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>C. pelagic</i> Rousselet, 1893	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
Colurella Bory de St. Vincent, 1824		
<i>C. adriatica</i> Ehrenberg, 1831	A3, A5, A6, D1, E1, E2, E3, E4 (A, D, E)	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>C. colurus</i> Ehrenberg, 1830	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>C. obtuse</i> Gosse, 1886	A2, A5, A6 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>C. uncinato bicuspidato</i> Ehrenberg, 1830	A2, A3 (A)	10, 11, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 33
<i>C. uncinata</i> O. F. Müller, 1773	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
Conochilus Ehrenberg, 1834		
<i>C. exiguous</i> Ahlstrom, 1938	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 42
<i>C. hippocrepsis</i> Schrank, 1830	A1, A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>C. unicornis</i> Rousselet, 1892	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 42
Dicranophorus Nitsch, 1827		
<i>D. forcipatus</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A2, E1 (A, E)	10, 11, 31
<i>D. grandis</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A5 (A)	14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
<i>D. rostratus</i> Dixon Nuttal et Freeman, 1902	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Dipleuchlanis de Beauchamp, 1910		
<i>D. propatula</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Dissotrocha Bryce, 1910		
<i>D. aculeata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A3, A5, A6 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Epiphanes Ehrenberg, 1832		
<i>E. macrourus</i> Barrois & Daday, 1894	A5, B1 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>E. senta</i> O.F. Müller, 1773	A5, B1 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Euchlanis Ehrenberg, 1832		
<i>E. dilatata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A2, A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>E. incise</i> Carlin, 1939	A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>E. meneta</i> Myers, 1930	A5 (A)	39, 41
Filinia Bory de St. Vincent, 1824		
<i>F. longiseta</i> Ehrenberg, 1834	A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, B1, B2, C4, C5, D1 (A, B, C, D)	2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 19, 20, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>F. opoliensis</i> Zacharias, 1898	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>F. terminalis</i> Plate, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42

Gastropus Imhof, 1898		
<i>G. hyptopus</i> Ehrenberg, 1838	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>G. stylifer</i> Imhof, 1891	A1, A2, A4, A5, B1, D1, E1 (A, B, D, E)	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 30, 31, 32, 38, 40, 41, 42
Hexarthra Schmarda, 1854		
<i>H. mira</i> Hudson, 1871	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Kellicottia Ahlstrom, 1938		
<i>K. longispina</i> Kellicott, 1879	A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, B1, B2, C1, C2, C3, C4, D1, E1 (A, B, C, D, E)	2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Keratella Bory de St. Vincent, 1822		
<i>K. cochlearis</i> Gosse, 1851	A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, B1, B2, C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, D1, E2 (A, B, C, D, E)	2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>K. cochlearis v. hispida</i> Lauterborn, 1898	A2 (A)	2, 25, 26, 36
<i>K. hiemalis</i> Carlin, 1943,	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>K. quadrata</i> O.F. Müller, 1786,	A1, A2, A5, D1, E2 (A, D, E)	2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15
<i>K. tecta</i> Gosse, 1851	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>K. ticinensis</i> Callerio, 1921	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>K. valga</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Lecane Nitzsch, 1827		
<i>L. bulla</i> Gosse, 1851	A2, A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. clostercerca</i> Schmarda, 1859	A2, A3, A5, B1 (A, B)	2, 13, 14, 15, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>L. copeis</i> Harring et Myers, 1926	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. curvirostris</i> Yamamoto, 1941	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. elasma</i> Harring & Myers, 1926	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. elsa</i> Nitzsch, 1827	A5, A6 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. flexilis</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. hamata</i> Stokes, 1896	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. ivli</i> Wiszniewski, 1935	A2, A5 (A)	2, 13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. lamellate</i> Daday, 1893	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. luna</i> O.F. Müller, 1776	A1, A2, A3, B1 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. lunaris</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A3 (A)	3, 9, 23, 24, 25, 29
<i>L. nana</i> Murray, 1913	A5, B2 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. quadridentata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. obtusa</i> Hauer, 1889	A5 (A)	2, 13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. stenroosi</i> Meissner, 1908	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Lepadella Bory de St. Vincent, 1826		
<i>L. acuminata</i> Ehrenberg, 1834	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. ehrenbergii</i> Perty, 1850	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. ovalis</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. patella</i> O.F. Müller, 1773	A2, A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. rhomboides</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	1, 2, 13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. triptera</i> Ehrenberg, 1830	A2, A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Lophocharis Ehrenberg, 1838		
<i>L. oxysternon</i> Gosse, 1851	A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>L. salpina</i> Ehrenberg, 1834	A5, A6 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Monommata Bartsch, 1870		
<i>M. aequalis</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Mytilina Bory de St. Vincent, 1826		
<i>M. crassipes</i> Luchs, 1912	A5 (A)	1, 2, 13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>M. mucronata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>M. ventralis brevispina</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A2, A3 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39

<i>M. ventralis ventralis</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A2, A3 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39
Notholca Gosse, 1886		
<i>N. acuminatae</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A2, A3 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39
<i>N. foliacea</i> Ehrenberg, 1838	A5 (A)	1, 2, 13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>N. squamula</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A2 (A)	13, 14, 15, 30, 32, 38
Notommata Ehrenberg, 1830		
<i>N. copeus</i> Ehrenberg, 1834	A2, A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Philodina Ehrenberg, 1830		
<i>P. megalotrocha</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A3 (A)	36, 37
Plationus Segers, Murugan & Dumont, 1993		
<i>P. patulus</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A2, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Platylas Harring, 1913		
<i>P. quadricornis</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Ploesoma Herrick, 1885		
<i>P. hudsoni</i> Imhof, 1891	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 39, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>P. truncatum</i> Levander, 1894	A3, A4, A5, B1 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Polyarthra Ehrenberg, 1834		
<i>P. dolichoptera</i> Delson, 1925	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>P. euryptera</i> Wierzejski, 1891	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>P. major</i> Bueckhardt, 1900	A5, A5, B1, B2 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>P. minor</i> Voigt, 1904	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>P. remata</i> Skorikov, 1896	A5, B1, B2, E1 (A, B, E)	2, 13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39
<i>P. trygla</i> Ehrenberg, 1834	A1, A2, A3, A5, B1 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>P. vulgaris</i> Carlin, 1943	A1, A2, A3, A5, B1 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Pompholyx Gosse, 1851		
<i>P. complanata</i> Gosse, 1851	A5, A6 (A)	2, 13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39
<i>P. sulcata</i> Hudson, 1885	B1, B2, D, E1, E2 (B, D, E)	26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32
<i>P. triloba</i> Pejler, 1957	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Rotaria Scopoli, 1777		
<i>R. citrine</i> Ehrenberg, 1838	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>R. rotatoria</i> Pallas, 1766	A3, A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>R. socialis</i> Kellicot, 1888	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Scaridium Ehrenberg, 1830		
<i>S. longicaudum</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A3 (A)	7, 8, 35, 36, 37
Squatinella Bory de St. Vincent, 1826		
<i>S. lamellaris</i> O.F. Müller, 1786	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
Synchaeta Ehrenberg, 1832		
<i>S. littoralis</i> Rousselet, 1902	A5, A6, E1 (A, E)	13, 14, 15, 29, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>S. pectinata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	A1, A2, A5, A6, B1, B2, C1, C5 (A, B, C)	2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>S. stylata</i> Wierzejski, 1893	B1, B2, C1, C2, C3, C4, C5 (B, C)	27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32
Testudinella Bory de St. Vincent, 1826		
<i>T. mucronata</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. patina</i> Hermann, 1783	A2, A3 (A, B)	13, 14, 15, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. truncata</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
Trichocerca Lamarck, 1801		
<i>T. bicristata</i> Gosse, 1887	A3 (A)	5, 6, 7, 8, 35, 36
<i>T. capucina</i> Wie&Zach, 1893	A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, B1, B2, D, C3, C4, C5 (A, B, C)	2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 28, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. cylindrica</i> Imhof, 1891	A1, A2, A5 (A)	2, 28, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42

<i>T. elongate</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. iernis</i> Gosse, 1887	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>T. longiseta</i> Schrank, 1802	A1, A2, A3 (A)	13, 14, 15, 30, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>T. myersi</i> Hauer, 1931	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. porcellus</i> Gosse, 1886	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. pusilla</i> Lauterborn, 1898	A2, E3, E4 (A, E)	3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14
<i>T. rattus</i> O.F. Müller, 1776	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. rousseleti</i> Voigt, 1902)	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. similis</i> Wierzejski, 1893)	A1, A2, A5 (A)	2, 28, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42
<i>T. stylata</i> Gosse, 1851	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. tenuior</i> Gosse, 1886	A2 (A)	13, 14, 15, 30, 32, 38
<i>T. weberi</i> Jennings, 1903	A2, A3 (A)	2, 28, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 38
Trichotria Bory de St. Vincent, 1827		
<i>T. curta</i> Skorikov, 1914	A5 (A)	13, 14, 15, 31, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. pocillum</i> O.F. Müller, 1776	A3, A5 (A)	2, 13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42
<i>T. tetractis</i> Ehrenberg, 1830	A3, A5 (A)	2, 13, 14, 15, 39, 30, 32, 38, 39, 41, 42

Legends for letter symbols and nearest central point in brackets

A1 - Lake Micro Prespa (N:40.691447; E:21.028600),
A2 - Lake Macro Prespa (N:40.794431; E:20.946263),
A3 - Lake Ohrid (N:40.974442; E:20.676057),
A4 - Lake Fierza (N:42.090651; E:20.395832),
A5 - Lake Scadar/Shkodra (N:42.150502; E:19.395438),
A6 - River Buna (N:42.005522; E:19.456769),
B1 - Reservoir Bovilla (N:41.444056; E:19.893058),
B2 - Lake Tirana (N:41.310917; E:19.816143),
C1 - Lake Belshi (N:40.978345; E:19.891313),
C2 - Lake Merhoe (N:40.952991; E:19.899225),
C3 - Lake Seferani (N:40.940781; E:19.920761),
C4 - Reservoir Thana (N:40.862995; E:19.840817),
C5 - Reservoir Murrizi (N:40.727543; E:19.728467),
D1 - Lake Butrinti (N:39.784623; E:20.032498),
E1 - Lagoon of Patok (N:41.631068; E:19.601154),
E2 - Lagoon of Karavasta (N:40.918227; E:19.475840),
E3 - Lagoon of Narta (N:40.538250; E:19.424175),
E4 - Lagoon of Orikum (N:40.317013; E:19.441460),

Albanian water basin symbols in brackets from Dill (1993)

A (Drini Basin); B (Ishmi/Erzeni Basin); C (Semani Basin); D (Coastal Ionian Sea); E (Coastal Adriatic Sea).

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Acknowledgements – The research carried in last ten years was funded by the Ministry of Science, Youth and Sports from the Republic of Albania (Grants No.: 11/2009) and NRC Norway through the project on Interdisciplinary Study of Large Balkan Lakes (2008-2012).

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